

III ALAGOAS MULTIDISCIPLINARY CONGRESS ON CANCER

CAR-T CELL IMMUNOTHERAPY AND THE ADVERSE EFFECT OF NEUROTOXICITY: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Introduction: CAR-T cell therapy has been successful in cancer treatment; however, it can have serious adverse effects that are significant for the quality of life of cancer patients. **Objective:** To review the literature on the adverse effects of CAR-T cell neurotoxicity. **Method and materials:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflective, descriptive and qualitative analysis. Eight scientific articles published in the journals Nature, The Lancet and the National Institute of Health were used. **Results:** The adverse effect of neurotoxicity associated with CAR-T cell therapy is expressed through syndromes. Cytokine Release Syndrome (CRS) is an adverse effect that causes a systemic inflammatory response, mimicking sepsis, occurring when there is an exacerbated activation of immune system cells in the cytotoxic bias. It is an adverse effect that causes a toxic encephalopathy with a broad spectrum of neuropsychiatric symptoms. This syndrome is caused by a possible increase in the sensitivity of the blood-brain barrier, which is a serious sign that can lead the patient to organ failure and subsequent death. **Conclusion:** Because of these possible adverse effects, it is essential to monitor and follow up on cancer patients undergoing CAR-T cell therapy, given that the proper management of patients under these effects is intended to save their lives and provide continuity in therapy planning.

Keywords: Immunotherapy; CAR-T; Neurotoxicity.